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**THE PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE AND USE OF
SUPERCONDUCTIVITY.**

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Annotation. In the article, the author analyzed the processes of application of superconductors in medicine, transport, electronics and energy as examples of the practical importance of superconductivity physics. The article is written by recording useful information, physical characteristics of important technical indicators.

Key words: SQUID devices, lack of resistance, high-temperature superconductors, MRI devices, Maglev airbags, superconducting cables, superconducting power supply, Tokomak device.

Introduction. The field of application of superconductors is so wide that they range from very small SQUID devices to huge magnetic and electromagnetic devices.

Despite the fact that with the practical application of these conductors from the first days of its creation began to work, to this day, the possibility of its expansion is limited by temperature. Lack of resistance, first of all, in the field of energy, electrical engineering gives great results. The Meissner effect, the tunneling phenomenon, the Josephson effect, etc., which were later observed in superconductors, made it possible to use it on a large scale. Research is being conducted in laboratories and test sites around the world to develop equipment and devices that are extremely effective for humanity from these superconducting

properties. The discovery of high-temperature superconductors accelerated the work in this direction [1].

Methods. Let's take a look at some of the uses of different conductors. First of all, let's consider the use of superconductors in medicine.

Toshiba superconductors help in the treatment of cancer. In the 1980s, it became clear that magnetic resonance imaging using electromagnetic fields from superconductors could provide much more accurate diagnostics than newly developed computed tomography technology and older X-rays (figure 1). Toshiba understood that too. Since then, the company has become a supplier of superconducting magnets to manufacturers of medical devices and continues to this day. Medicine is developing, but various diseases are increasing. They also found a vaccine for the Covid-19 virus, which entered the world in 2020. They are the heroes of today. The contribution of physics to the field of medicine is enormous. In particular, the field of superconductivity is used in many areas of society.

Picture 1. One of the first superconducting magnets for MRI devices.

Modern medical devices are becoming a hybrid: they are used not only for diagnosis, but also in therapeutic devices using heavy particles. Their essence is that they produce rays with the accelerated movement of heavy particles, which are directed to the tumors in the human body. A strong magnetic field is required to accurately direct the rays of such particles. In the past, such machines were already used, but they could not control the path of the particles formed, so patients had to

constantly change their position to keep the affected parts of the body exposed to radiation, which is why patients with cancer it is not easy. Toshiba engineers then inserted superconducting magnets into the port a moving ring part of the emitter, similar to a portal. They were able to quickly change the strength of magnetic fields. This allowed the rays to be directed more precisely, and the movement of the portal allowed patients to remain calm during therapy (figure 2).

Figure 2. Apparatus for heavy particle therapy. The rotating portal has a superconducting electromagnet.

Superconductivity in transport. Railway engineers have long wondered how to use the huge magnetic fields created by superconductors (magnetic levitation) (figure 3). Due to the currents generated by the current in the guide conductor between the moving magnets and the moving magnet, the train can move smoothly without noise and friction and reach very high speeds. Japan is a leader in the application of superconductivity in railways. In Japan, the development of this route has been going on for about 20 years, during which time about 10 modifications of trains have been produced.

Figure 3. Picture of Yamanashi MLX01 train moving (Japan).

Maglev or magnetic levitation is hard to explain - a complex technology that allows an object like shinkansen to float on rails, but the center does it in an incredible way.

Advantages of Maglev airbags:

1. Trains running on a magnetic cushion can increase the speed compared to conventional trains. It also saves passengers time.
2. Magnetically inflated trains make less noise than conventional trains.
3. Magnetically-powered trains use low-energy sources of air pollution.
4. The huge potential for increasing the speed, the possibility of increasing the speed many times over the speed of jet aviation. Such a speed is achieved by reducing the aerodynamic resistance, ie the train is placed in a high vacuum tunnel.

Disadvantages of trains running on a magnetic cushion:

1. The cost of trains running on a magnetic cushion is more expensive than conventional trains.
2. Special training is required for train personnel moving on a magnetic cushion.

3. An electromagnet on the rails is used to create levitation on trains running on a superconducting magnetic pad. This raises the issue of protection of passengers from the effects of strong magnetic fields, ie shielding.
4. Strong side winds can also affect train movement. Snow or ice on the rails can also be a problem.
5. A sudden drop in voltage leads to the derailment of train cars moving on a superconducting magnetic pad. This can be very dangerous when driving at high speeds [10].

Figure 4. The process of preparing the Maglev train for movement.

The Maglev train returned 581 km/h in 2003, the fastest rail speed in the world to date. The record is currently 603 km/h, which was introduced in 2015 on test tracks. However, commercial trains on the new Chuo Shinkansen maglev line will reach 500 km/h. These trains run on a magnetic cushion (figure 4).

Results. Another use of superconductors for power generation is the presence of powerful small-sized current generators. Superconducting electric motors create magnetic fields in generators and electric motors, making them much more powerful than conventional machines. Large prototypes could have been created long ago, and ceramic superconductors made such machines powerful. In the magnetohydrodynamics of thermonuclear energy, the possibility of using

superconducting magnets to store electricity is also considered. For production, in 2005, Siemens announced that it had created the first powerful generator with a high-temperature generator (figure 5). The power of the generator is 4000 kilowatts. The company has announced its readiness to sell this type of generators. Their cost is very high, but the use of superconductivity (calculations show that, first of all, the use in a confined space, for example, on ships) is useful. The advantages of superconducting generators are clear: its weight and geometric dimensions are twice less than conventional generators with similar power. High-temperature superconducting generators show high voltage stability against load changes and high reactive power consumption.

Figure 5. High-temperature superconducting generator of Siemens concern and generator developed at Elektromash Research Institute.

The potentially most useful industrial application of superconductors in the transmission of electricity is associated with the production, transmission and use of electricity. For example, superconducting cables with a diameter of a few inches can carry a lot of electricity, like a huge transmission line, without losses. With the advent of liquid nitrogen-cooled ceramic superconductors, the transmission of electricity using superconductors has become very cost-effective (table 1 and figure 6).

Project name, country	Southwire- ULTRA USA, Denmark	Albany project USA, Japan	LIPA project USA, France Germany	Super-ACE Japan
Trial period	In August 2006 started	Started in July 2006	Started in 2007	In 2005 finished
Material	Bi- 2223 tape AMSC	Bi- 2223 tape Sumitomo	Bi- 2223 tape AMSC	Bi- 2223 tape Furukawa
Cable type	Triaxial	'three together' plus coupling	In individual cryostats 3 separate phases	Single phase
Operating voltage, kW	13	34.5	138	77
Transmitted Power, MBA	69	48	574	133
Rated operating current, A	3000	800	2400	1400
Number of phases	3	3	3	1
Length, m	200	350 (320 + 30)	660	500
Outer diameter, Mm	143	135	–	133
Maximum current, kA	20	23	69	–

Maximum duration, sec	–	0.63 (0.13 da tested)	0.35	–
Refrigerant temperature, K	65-80	67-77	65-71	65-77
Cryogenic device manning power, kW	2	5 (77 K)	More than 13	6 (77 K)
Maximum refrigerant consumption, L / min	–	50	–	100
Refrigerant pressure, atm	–	1-3	2.6-7.5	–

Table 1. Efficiency indicators for the use of superconducting cables.

Figure 6. The structure of superconducting cables is described. Their characteristics are given in the table below as an example.

The table above shows that high-power cables manufactured by companies in different countries can be cooled with liquid nitrogen in addition to cooling with liquid helium, in which case the transmission capacity is reduced to a certain extent. The values of critical temperature and critical magnetic field of type I and type II superconducting materials are shown in the table below (table 2).

CRITICAL TEMPERATURE AND MAGNETIC FIELD

Materials	Critical temperature, K	Critical magnetic field (at 0 K) Gs	
Type I superconductors			
Rhodium	0.000325	0.049	
Titan	0.39	60	
Cadmium	0.52	28	
Zinc	0.65	55	
Galliy	1.08	59	
Tally	2.37	180	
Now	3.41	280	
Tin	3.72	305	
Mercury	4.15	411	
Lead	7.19	603	
Round 2 superconductors			
	H_{c1}	H_{c2}	
Niobium	9.25	1738	4040
Nb ₃ Sn	18.1	-	220000
Nb ₃ Ge	23.2	-	400000
Pb ₁ Mo _{5,1} S ₆	14.4	-	600000
YBa ₂ Cu ₃ O ₇	90-100	1000	1,000,000
Extrapolated to absolute zero			

Table 2. Critical temperature and critical magnetic field values of type I and type II superconductor materials.

Discussion. Conducting magnets are represented by special electromagnets. They have a magnetic field created by electric currents passing through superconductors, which have minimal or zero resistance (figure 7).

Let's get acquainted with the principle of operation of conductive magnets. The main condition for maintaining zero resistance is to lower the temperature to a

certain value, which depends on the material of the superconductor in the winding. To minimize gas evaporation, the vessel is immersed in another duar vessel, but this time liquid nitrogen is applied (figure 8).

Figure 7. Superconducting magnet.

Figure 8. 1-network, 2liquid helium, 3-solenoid, 4 - a device used to connect and disconnect strong electrical currents, 5-DC power supply, 6-spiral for heating.

In this case, the winding of the superconducting magnet has zero resistance. Even if it is tightly closed, the electricity supplied to it will flow for as long as we

want. Due to the fact that the current does not slow down and rotates in the winding without waves, the magnetic field is the same, which allows to create optimal conditions for different scientific research. The superconducting magnet has a large force, so diamagnetic materials begin to float in the air in their field. Lead, which is not attracted by ordinary magnets, also affects superconducting devices. With this, even light organic matter begins to float in the air. Experiments with a superconducting magnet allowed small rodents and frogs to be lifted into the air by a magnetic field. To ensure the levitation of small living things, 16 Tesla induction field must be created.

As the temperature rises, the superconducting devices lose their properties. Various niobium alloys are used in the manufacture of magnetic coils. In particular, it is combined with zirconium, titanium and tin. Sometimes an alloy of vanadium and gallium is used. Used to strengthen packaging materials in copper or aluminum electromagnets. They are very thin, which reduces heat generation. Copper or aluminum itself uses 5 to 50% of the superconductor, the proportion of which depends on the size of the magnet. To cool the device, the packaging is lined with cavities to ensure efficient circulation of liquid helium.

In traditional conductors, the energy cycle causes them to heat up. This is due to the collision of the atoms of the crystal lattice of the superconducting material. As a result, the current is lost, which goes in the form of partial heat release. Thus, it is not necessary to constantly expend energy on the main purpose to overcome resistance. The current itself is generated by an electron flow. In superconductors, energy is transferred by paired electrons called pairs. They move without resistance between the crystal lattices of the superconducting metal, which eliminates energy loss and does not cause overheating.

Superconducting magnets require a special startup to work. First, a special heater is turned on inside them, which is located in the closing coil. The temperature of the wire is transferred to its critical temperature, and thus the circuit loses its conductivity. When the required current is reached, the heater switches off. In

addition, the electron is cooled and has superconducting properties. When the desired low temperature is reached, the power supply is reduced to zero, at the same time the superconducting magnet begins to circulate and an inexhaustible current begins to flow (figure 9).

Figure 9. Superconducting power supply.

Depending on the properties of the conductor, the magnet can produce a field strength of up to 200 kg. The largest superconducting device is a magnet, which was used in 2014 as a central part of a large hadron collider. Despite the enormous power of superconducting magnets, the cost of charging them is 500 times less than using conventional electromagnets with similar field strength. Up to 150 kW of power is required to power the device. For comparison, water-cooled structural magnets require up to 60 MW. However, the construction costs of both devices are approximately the same. Superconducting magnets are commonly used as research to study the electrical and optical properties of various substances. Modern experiments in the study of plasma, as well as elementary particles, are carried out under field conditions created by such magnets. In addition to laboratory applications, low-power magnets are used in radio wave applications.

In the future, it can be noted that such devices can be used as an inductive energy storage device, which, unlike ordinary batteries, can hold an unlimited

charge. So far, the use of magnets in this direction has not been widely used, but it can not be said that there have been no attempts.

Figure 10. Tokomak device.

Thus, 600 MJ of energy is stored in Tokomak (magnetic plasma chamber), which is 166 kW. The design of the international experimental fusion nuclear reducer ITER has a high performance, which accumulates 11000 kW (figure 10). There is also example of using superconductor efficiently in energy systems. Hydrogen, which is said to be main source of the fututrem can become a much-needed fuel for the transportation industry. On the other hand, in order to have a stable and long-term market for hydrogen energy that can meet the needs of the transport sector, it is necessary to address many technological elements that primarily affect the cost of vehicles and fuel [4,9]. In transportation of hydrogen, superconductors can be used in many processes [1-8].

Conclusions. Superconducting magnets are promising devices that are constantly evolving. More and more superconductors are used to create them, which are created experimentally by scientists. This allows the magnets to reduce energy consumption for self-charging, as well as achieve high power with the reduced size of the devices. The existing devices are characterized by high weight and size, as well as high production costs, so they are gradually being introduced into everyday life.

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